

SIMULATION OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION SITUATIONS AT DIFFERENT LEVELS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Abstract:

Within the framework of the concept of modernizing Uzbek education, the issues of communicative teaching of the English language acquire special significance, since communicative competence is aimed at achieving practical results in mastering the English language, as well as at educating, training, and developing the student as a personality.

Keywords: communication, foreign language, speech, linguistic, sociocultural, compensatory, educational, cognitive.

The national educational standard for foreign languages sets goals for achieving qualitatively new outcomes in language learning, particularly: the development of its components — speech, linguistic, sociocultural, compensatory, educational, and cognitive elements of communicative competence in a foreign language.

It is known that building a communicative learning process first and foremost requires the modeling of situations as units of communication and the formation of their functional aspects. A situation is a form of functioning of communication, a unit of communication in which the educational process is built as a model of the communication process.

In communicative teaching, situations are not used only at the final stage of material acquisition, but serve as an essential foundation at all stages of learning and form the basis for managing the process of mastering communication in a foreign language.

A situation is a complex phenomenon that requires a broad and in-depth approach to study. It is important to find methodologically correct criteria for modeling an oral speech situation.

It is known that success in teaching foreign languages is determined by the proper organization of the educational process. Engaging students in active speech activity in the classroom is the responsibility of the teacher. Therefore, one of the most effective means of revealing students' creative potential is teaching them how to communicate.

In practice, teaching students natural communication in a foreign language is a difficult task.

In the process of communication, various forms of activity are realized (educational-cognitive, socio-political, labor, sports, artistic, everyday life).

The content of communication represents a challenge based on the subjects of discussion.

Modeling real-life speech communication situations in the classroom is the foundation of foreign language learning.

This is a technology that contributes to the development of competencies. It can be applied at various stages of teaching English and helps to improve students' speaking and writing skills, expand their vocabulary, and broaden their linguistic horizons.

E.I. Passov identifies several types of situations:

Situations of social and status relationships.

(A lesson in the format of a teleconference, discussion of the rights and responsibilities of citizens of other countries, conversations with foreigners about traditions, customs, and life in the target-language country)

Situations of role relationships.

(Acting out informal roles in oral communication helps to better understand the relationships between children, influences students' personal qualities, and affects their motivation to learn the language)

Situations of joint activity.

(Exchange of experience, working in groups)

Situations of moral relationships.

Real-life situations are conditions as close to real life as possible. To ensure that educational speech situations are as realistic as possible, it is important that participants are genuinely interested in the content of the conversation and feel the need to conduct it in the foreign language. Main parameters for modeling real speech communication situations:

motivation

purposefulness

informativeness of the communication process

novelty

situational relevance

nature of interaction between communicants

system of speech tools

Conditions for creating real communication situations:

defining communicative tasks connected with the student's personality and life, affecting their emotional and intellectual spheres;

using various stimulating tools, taking into account the characteristics of students of different ages, their levels of knowledge, skills, and abilities;

encouraging students to express their attitude toward what they have heard, seen, or read.

Simulating real speech communication situations in English in the classroom is a method of immersing students into natural communication environments. It stimulates imagination, encourages them to express their thoughts and feelings, and activates everyday vocabulary, speech formulas, and grammatical structures without specifically focusing attention on them.

Modeling real communication situations can be implemented through the following exercises:

1. Presenting a topic related to the given situation, taking into account the communicative task (speech behavior tactics, established patterns);
2. A sequence of images with key words (illustrating the sequence of actions);
3. Story pictures with a simple (or complex) undeveloped situation;
4. Simulation of situations based on videos and presentations;
5. Based on reporting information;
6. Using existing data on the situation, such as the beginning and end of a dialogue;
7. Based on key words;
8. Based on visual stimuli and key words;
9. Texts with an undeveloped situation;
10. Developing and expanding monologic speech by bringing the second part to life;
11. Modeling situations in new conditions within the framework of the studied topic.
12. Typical speech situations related to the topic;
13. Creating micro-dialogues on various topics;
14. Composing various dialogues and micro-dialogues for communication in a polylogue (discussions, press conferences, teleconferences);
15. Based on a number of proposed situations.

Practice shows that the greatest potential for modeling speech situations is revealed through children's play activities. At the early stages of learning,

students enjoy imaginary situations with elements of role play. It is at this stage that speech situations help enhance the educational effect.

In Grade 5, simple situations can be offered:

"You meet a tourist from the UK. Let's get to know them better" —
"Communication" – "Getting acquainted."

Situations can be modeled in different ways: visualization, oral description, dramatization.

For example, while studying the topic "Family" in Grade 5, students can bring photos of their family members. Such tasks can be suggested:

- "Natasha, show us the photos of your family members and tell us about them."

The class should be ready to ask questions.

Similarly, while studying the topic "Free time," you can offer this situation:

"Vika loves music very much. Listen to her talk about her favorite hobby and ask her questions."

For example, while studying the topic "Travel," you can review the topics "My city," "My village." Suggested situations:

"Your weekend plans,"

"Your upcoming holiday plans,"

"You are sitting on a train. Describe what you see through the window,"

"Help your mom pack for the trip."

Students should be encouraged not to limit themselves to the current topic but to expand their speech, connecting it with previously studied themes.

Speech situations are viewed as samples of real-life contexts in which students of a certain age willingly and actively speak in a foreign language in line with the age-appropriate curriculum. Using situational pictures helps activate students' speaking skills.

Based on memory and accumulated knowledge, they can select what's necessary to talk about in a particular situation and speak using the pictures.

Students themselves become actors.

It is important to give such tasks that stimulate their creative thinking, such as puzzles, riddles, and more.

Examples of tasks:

1. Form a new word:

1. A new word is formed from the names of two objects indicated by numbers (e.g., "book" + "shelf" = bookshelf);

2. If a letter is shown above the picture, it should be inserted into the word to form a new one (three options);

3. If a letter is crossed out in the image, it should be removed; if another letter is next to it, it replaces the first one;

4. Adding a letter (or letters) to the name of the object forms a new word (example: "this");

5. If a comma stands before the number, the first letter (or word) of the object's name is removed. If the comma is after the number, the last letter is silent;

6. If two objects are shown together, the preposition "in" should be recalled (for example: wind in singing).

2. By reading the letters step by step, you will discover a new English proverb.

An arrow shows which letter to start from.

Example proverb: "Every dog has its day."

(There will be a holiday).

3. Restore the word order in the interrogative sentence.

Then answer the question. Do you want to ask a question? (Do you like asking questions?)

Gradually, children begin to complete such tasks independently. In doing so, they firmly acquire the lexical material, memorize the spelling of words, and learn how to use a dictionary.

By using all these methods, the teacher defines the main goal of establishing contact with students — namely, to teach them to feel free and relaxed during the lesson. This contributes to successful communication in English and, as a result, helps achieve good academic outcomes.

In conclusion, I would like to emphasize that modeling real-life speech situations in English lessons:

contributes to the formation of key competencies;

helps the teacher solve communicative tasks directly related to the goals and content of learning;

reduces students' fatigue;

improves the quality of education;

ensures the developmental and problem-based nature of learning;

stimulates students' speech and cognitive development, fosters their curiosity, determination, and diligence;

introduces students to the cultural values of another nation.

All the above-mentioned methods of modeling real communicative situations in foreign language lessons can be integrated at various stages of the lesson, depending on its type, the complexity of the material, the preparedness of the class, and the teacher's creative abilities.

References:

1. Davydova O. I., Mayer A. A., Bogoslavets L. G. "Interactive Methods for Organizing Pedagogical Councils in Preschool Educational Institutions", Publisher: Detstvo-Press, 2010.
2. Mushtavinskaya I. V. "Technology of Developing Critical Thinking", Study Guide, 2015.
3. Belaya K. Yu. Methodical Work in Preschool Educational Institutions: Analysis, Planning, Forms and Methods — Moscow: SC Sfera, 2005 — 96 pages..

